

APPLICATION OF STEAM TECHNOLOGY IN VARIOUS GROUPS OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

Ashurova Zarina Muxitdinovna

Bukhara State Pedagogical Institute,
teacher of the department of preschool education

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Annotation. The article describes the role of STEAM technology in the preschool education system, the use of STEAM technology from simple to complex in different age groups of preschool educational organizations: junior, middle, senior and preparatory groups for school.

Keywords. STEAM technology, science - science, technology - technology, reading - reading, engineering - engineering, art - art.

Around the world, quality preschool education is defined as an important investment in the development of human capital, ensuring its achievements in public life. Based on international experience, the use of technologies that ensure the mental potential, emotional and physical health of children in the educational process, raising the quality of school training to a new level, innovative approaches expressed in the UN sustainable development goals until 2030. A significant improvement in the process based on the use of STEAM technology was noted as one of the main indicators.

Shtanko Dmitry Nikolaevich, one of the Russian scientists, in his study stated that "STEAM technology in preschool education will help our children become the next generation of inventors and leaders, conduct research like scientists, model like technologists, create designs like engineers." "The Science area of STEAM technology includes natural sciences such as biology, zoology, anatomy, chemistry, geography, geology, physics. The Technology area of STEAM technology includes subjects such as computer science and robotics. The Engineering area business" knows how to develop and apply engineering

principles. The "Arts" area includes visual arts, music, choreography, theater and even foreign languages. The "Mathematics" area: consists of subjects such as mathematics, algebra, technology-based education. STEAM is developing every day as one of the main global trends and is based on the application of an interdisciplinary, practical approach to activities, as well as the integration of technology and natural sciences into a single educational direction developing STEAM technology (using the example of the STEAM laboratory), ensuring the continuity of STEAM education, dividing preschoolers into groups depending on their abilities according to a modular principle. , organizing practical activities, and in the process of practical activities, children are required to independently collect their ideas based on experience and exchange ideas.

As we know, STEAM is a method of harmonious teaching of science, technology, engineering, art and mathematics, which produces thousands. The student develops innovative thinking, finding multiple solutions to a problem, and creativity, which will be very useful in his future career. This approach will help children solve life problems in the future. In the last decade, STEAM has been viewed as a strategy for sustainable development, a concept for quality education and an interdisciplinary holistic model of education that helps solve social, environmental and economic problems associated with the technological development of countries. STEAM education is most effective when it is provided in the early years and when it increases children's motivation to learn and connects STEAM subjects to their careers, as well as when they focus on self-development and active citizenship.

Today, STEAM education is developing as one of the main trends in the world and is based on the integration of five areas into a single educational scheme using a practical approach. The conditions for such education are its continuity and the development of children's ability to communicate in groups where they can collect and exchange ideas. Therefore, the basic educational program includes modules for the development of logical thinking, such as Lego technologies and

activities with children. Thanks to the STEAM approach, children understand nature and regularly explore the world, thereby learning their interests, the engineering way of thinking, the ability to get out of critical situations, the development of teamwork and the basics of leadership, self-expression, which in turn provides a completely new level of children's development. Strengthening self-confidence. With this approach, children "launch" hand-made bridges and roads, airplanes and cars, "develop" and test underwater and aerial structures, each time getting closer to the goal. A "product" that does not give good results is repeatedly tested and improved. As a result, solving all problems independently and achieving goals brings children inspiration, victory, adrenaline and joy. Every victory gives you more confidence in your abilities. Teaches active communication and teamwork. STEAM programs also feature teaching about active communication and teamwork. During the discussion stage, children learn not to be afraid to express their opinions. During classes, children do not sit frontally at a table, but test and develop "products" based on their own designs. During activities, children are always busy communicating with teachers and their friends in a team that ensures cooperation [30; 23-36]. Development of interests in technical sciences. The task of STEAM education in preschool and primary school age is to create the initial conditions for the development of interest. In natural and technical sciences for children, the basis for developing interest is love for what they do.

STEAM is very interesting and dynamic for children, which does not let them get bored. They do not notice the passage of time, but do not get tired S - science - natural science T - technology - technology E - engineering - engineering A - art - art M - mathematics - mathematics. These directions are the most popular system in the modern world. Therefore, today the STEAM system is developing as one of the main directions. The direction of STEAM education and the use of a practical approach are also based on the integration of all five areas into a single educational system. Some schools embrace the talents of their graduates and

integrate subjects such as science, technology, engineering and mathematics, and this is how the STEM system was formed. (Science, technology, engineering and mathematics). Later Art was added here, and finally STEAM was formed. Teachers believe that knowledge of these subjects, or rather these subjects, will help students become highly qualified specialists in the future. In STEAM technology, children strive for a better education. If we say that the main goal of traditional education is to teach knowledge and use this knowledge for thinking and creativity, then the STEAM approach teaches us to combine acquired knowledge with real-world skills.

At the international conference, issues of involving preschool children in STEAM education and the development of STEAM programs for children 3-7 years old were discussed. During the discussion, scientists proposed a special approach to educating girls using STEAM technology, setting the stage for future success in science and making the programs interesting for children. It was unanimously decided that the international language of STEAM education is English.

In the Russian Federation, there is growing attention to the use of STEAM education in all areas. In order to interest children in technical subjects, IT classes, STEAM laboratories and LEGO centers are being created in educational institutions: preschool educational organizations, clubs, schools.

STEAM education is an integral part of projects created in the Russian education system. The inclusion of STEAM education in the national program largely depends on the creation of a new subject-spatial environment of the entire educational system, updating its content, software and methodological support. But due to the lack of STEAM laboratories in many educational institutions, it is difficult to give children enough knowledge.

Classes are organized in modules based on STEAM technology - compared to traditional teaching methods, the STEAM approach allows children to conduct

experiments, build models, independently create music and films, bring their ideas to life, and the “subject” itself encourages the child to create.

Currently, priority is given to the technical direction. The format of additional education and training for children is changing. If children are taught using STEAM technology in preschool educational institutions, they will be able to independently conduct innovative research when they reach school age.

The goal of STEAM - educational technology is the development of intellectual abilities by involving children in scientific and technical creativity using modern information and communication technologies.

Based on STEAM technology, STEAM programs have been created in developed countries to provide education and training to children of preschool and school age. In such a program, children are not formed in every possible way in the strict regulation and education of children's knowledge. Based only on independent, free experience, he relies on the principles necessary for him to act, feel, think and perceive.

In Russia, a special program has been developed to introduce STEAM technology in preschool educational organizations and schools. The program was created by Russian scientists and created for children from 3 to 11 years old based on the instructions of the great thinkers of their time and modern foreign professors on the intellectual education of children. In the program, the formation of children's knowledge and skills is based first on the organization of STEAM education in a preschool educational organization, and then on practical exercises in laboratories, conditions for continuing education in technical and natural sciences at school.

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